

ANALYSIS OF INDIVIDUAL ATTITUDES AND PERCEPTIONS OF PERSONNEL PERFORMANCE WITH MOTIVATION VARIABLES AS INTERVENING IN THE DIRECTORATE FOR SECURITY OF VITAL OBJECTS AT POLDA XYZ

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Abstract

The following research aims to analyze the influence of individual attitudes, individual perceptions, individual work motivation, and personnel performance in the Ditpamobvit Polda XYZ organizational environment. In this case, the motivation in this study becomes the intervening variable. The research uses descriptive quantitative as the methodology with a causal relationship approach. The primary data collection process was carried out through a direct questionnaire technique to 280 respondents based on Slovin sampling. Meanwhile, data analysis using Structural Equation Model (SEM) with SmartPLS (Partial Least Square) 3.0. The results of data analysis show that: (i) individual attitudes partially have an indirect effect on personnel performance, (ii) individual perceptions partially have an indirect effect on personnel performance, and (iii) individual attitudes and perceptions partially and together have a positive and significant influence on personnel performance, (iv) Simultaneously or jointly between the variables of work motivation, attitude and individual perception has a positive and significant influence on personnel performance.

Keywords: Attitude, Perception, Work Motivation, Performance, Ditpamobvit

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the work units of the National Police which is an element of implementing the main tasks of the National Police in the field of security development and maintenance is the National Police Security Guard Agency (Baharkam). Baharkam's main duties are described in several functions, one of which is the Security of Vital Objects (PamObvit). In specific, the safeguarding of vital objects is regulated based on Presidential Decree No. 63 of 2004 concerning the Security of National Vital Objects.

The Vital Objects in question include national vital objects and specific objects which are local/district, architecture/construction, and/or employment that concern the livelihoods of many people, state interests, and/or strategic sources of state revenue; managed by the state, state-owned enterprises, regional-owned enterprises, national and foreign private vital objects.

The role of Securing Vital Objects is increasing important amid increasing varied security threats due to technological developments, as well as the challenges of national economic recovery after the Covid 19 storm. On the other hand, modern police science is advancing, demanding the ability of very complete police personnel, both hard skills and soft skills.

Several studies on attitudes, perceptions, motivation, and performance have been carried out. Employee attitudes affect motivation (Cabrera and Estacio, 2022; Kapantow, Luddin, and Kambey, 2020); or it may fail to achieve a motivational effect (Idowu, 2019). Several studies have also shown that all factors related to attitude have a positive effect on employee performance (Karlsson, Jensen, and Björklund, 2022; Divine, 2016; Cabrera and Estacio, 2022; Ogilo, Elenwo, Ojofeitimi, 2020). Previous research has also analyzed perceptions, attitudes, and performance (Soetomo and Hendrajaya, 2015; Mabenge, 2018; Haresaku et al., 2020; Cabrera and Estacio, 2022).

The lengthen to which employees are motivated in their work depends on how good the employee can provide output in their work. Several studies discuss motivation that has a positive effect on performance quality (Qadir, Saeed, & Khan, 2017; Diamantidis & Chatzoglou, 2018; Mensah, 2015; Tawiah, 2015; Saluy & Wibowo, 2018, Saluy & Tereshia, 2018; Pujiwati & Susanti, 2015). Employees characterized by high levels of motivation show higher job and life satisfaction (Khan, Dongping, and Ghauri, 2014).

The concept of attitude and perception is considered by others management experts as a very crucial factors in the context of modern managerial and marketing scientific literature because it is related to individual motivation. While motivation is closely related to the performance produced by individual employees. In today's, in the advanced multiple business environment, employees must have a certain growth regarding career choice and professional evolution.

The right motivation will be the best motivation to achieve high performance. The higher the motivation, the higher the employee performance. This shows that Employee Work Motivation can cause an increase or decrease in the amount of work productivity (Saluy and Wibowo, 2018). Furtwangler (2002: 86) identifies aspects of performance including loyalty, quality, discipline, values, and interpersonal skills.

Attitudes and perceptions have a significant influence on employee performance which in turn determines organizational performance to be excellent. Attitude is the covert and difficult-to-measure factors that ultimately becomes very important for the success of a company (Ilahi & Ahmad, 2016). Therefore, employee motivation must consider several variables that can influence it. The results of this research prove that motivation, work discipline, and allowance together have a positive and significant effect on employee performance

In this study, employees refer to personnel from Ditpamobvit Polda XYZ. This study considers the effect that the relationship between Ditpamobvit personnel's attitudes and perceptions about the organization has on their motivation. According to the explanation above, the researcher intends to conduct research regarding the values, attitudes, and motivations observed in the organizational environment of the Directorate for Security of Vital Objects (Ditpamobvit) Polda XYZ.

A preliminary survey conducted by researchers to 40 respondents from Ditpamobvit Polda XYZ personnel regarding perceptions, attitudes, motivation, and performance showed mixed results. Scores for these attitudes ranged from 60% to 70%. Based on the explanation of the background of the study and some preceding research on employee performance, the authors

intend to conduct research with the title Influence of Attitudes and Perceptions on Personnel Performance in the Directorate for Security of Vital Objects at Polda XYZ with Motivational Variables as Intervening.

2. STUDY OF THEORY

2.1. Attitude

Attitudes are evaluative statements - either favorable or unfavorable - about objects, people, or events (Robbins, 2003: 90). To determine what drives employee attitudes toward achieving company goals, Milman (2002) in the research of Ogilo, Elenwo, Ojofeitimi (2020) suggests the following as determinant factors of employee attitudes, factors such as job satisfaction, commitment, motivation, and training & development . This is supported by the view of Saari (2000) who suggests that communication, motivation, job satisfaction, and commitment are key predictors of employee attitudes in organizations.

In this study, the focus of attention on Attitude is related to three things, namely: job satisfaction, job complicity, and appointment to the organization. Job satisfaction is the effectiveness or emotional response to various aspects of work. Job complicity is the involvement of a person with a role in his work. Organizational appointment reflects how an individual determines with the organization and is bound by its goals (Kreitner & Kinicki, 2003; 270 – 274).

2.2. Perception

Perception according to Kreitner & Kinicki (2003) is a cognitive process that allows us to interpret and understand our environment. Robbins (2003) explains perception as a process that involves the senses. Perception does not just appear, few factors influence a individual's perception according on the individual's capability to respond to stimuli. Reception of stimuli is highly choosy and may be narrowed by an individual's beliefs, attitudes, motivations, and personality (Assael, 1995). Some persons are faced to choose stimuli that delight their urgent needs (perceptual vigilance). In the other side, it may ignore stimuli that can cause psychological anxiety (perceptual defense). Restiyanti, (2005:69), states that the factors that influence perception can be categorized into two main factors. First factor is internal factors, namely factors that come from within including on; include: a) Experience; b) Needs; c) Assessment; and d) Expectations. The seconds called external factors other factors that come from outside one's self in creating and finding something, such as a) External appearance; b) The nature of the stimulus; and c) The environmental situation.

2.3. Motivation

Motivation is described as the willingness to tackle to a higher level towards reaching an organizational target on the situation that it does not neglect its capability to obtain amusement in fulfilling personal needs (Hasibuan 2007:141). Hasibuan also links motivation as the best motivation that creates an individual's work enthusiasm so that they want to work in a group, work effectively, and be integrated with all their attempt to achieve satisfaction.

Motivation in this study will be focused on organizational goals related to work. There are 3 keywords: intensity, purpose, and persistence. High intensity will not produce results without being directed to a goal that is to benefit the organization. While the dimension of persistence in motivation is a measure of how long a person can maintain his business (Robbins, 2003).

2.4. Performance

The definition of performance (Colquitt et al, 2019:35) said that performance is the expense of a series of employee behaviors that contribute, both positively and negatively. The achievement is to complete the organizational target. In a simpler opinion, (Gibson, et al, 2012:374) states that performance is the outcome of work linked to organizational targets such as quality, efficiency, and other effective performance.

Performance is the outcome or level of achievement that determine an individual as a whole during a specific period in doing tasks that correlate to work standards, targets, or criteria that have been determined previously and have been jointly agreed upon (Rivai and Fawzi, 2004). Performance is the outcome of work in quality and quantity reached by an employee during doing his duties responsibly (Mangkunegara, 2017: 93). According to Gomes (2003: 135), several dimensions or criteria that need attention in measuring performance include (1) Work Quantity; (2) Work Quality; (3) Job Knowledge; (4) Reactiveness; (5) Cooperation; (6) Dependability; (7) Initiative; and (8) Individual Qualities.

2.5. Research Framework

Figure 1: Thinking Framework

3. RESEARCH METHOD

This research uses a survey research design with quantitative descriptive methods with a causal relationship approach. A quantitative approach to reveal the relationship or influence more precisely so that it can be said to be strong, low, or high (Rakhmat & Ibrahim, 2017). The research location of Ditpamobvit Polda XYZ is May 1 – June 31, 2022. The sampling technique was taken from a population of 938 personnel of Ditpamobvit Polda XYZ using the Slovin

formula (Silalahi, 2017: 389), so that a sample of 280 respondents with different characteristics regarding age, length of service was obtained, gender, and level of education.

The data used are primary data through a questionnaire using an ordinal Likert scale of 1-5. Data were analyzed using the systematic methods with Structural Equation Model (SEM), specifically SmartPLS (Partial Least Square) 3.0. The indicators with acceptance criteria can be seen in the following table:

Table 1: Rules of Thumb PLS

Test	Parameter	Criteria
Convergent Validity	Outer Loading	> 0.7
Discriminant Validity	AVE	> 0.5
Reliability	Composite Reliability	≥0.7
	Cronbach Alpha	≥0.7
Goodness of Fit	R-Square	> 0.67
Hypothesis Testing	Path Coefficient	P-Values < 0.05
	Indirect Effect	P-Values < 0.05
	T-Statistic	1,978

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Descriptive Analysis of Research Variables

Based on the results of distributing questionnaires to 280 respondents from the Ditpamobvit personnel of Polda XYZ. It is known that for the individual attitude variable, it can be seen that the average respondent who answered strongly agreed (SS) was 42.7%, answered Agree (S) was 40.3%, was neutral (N) was 14.4%, stated Disagree (TS) as much as 1.8%, and strongly disagree (STS) as much as 0.8%. Based on the average respondents' answers above, it proves that the average respondents have a positive attitude towards Pamobvit Polda XYZ. The statement that has the largest value according to the respondent's approval is statement item number 1 at 45% while the statement item with the smallest value according to the respondent's perception is statement item number 5 at 39.3%.

Perception variable data shows that the average respondents who answered strongly agree (SS) as much as 28%, agree (S) as much as 38.5%, being neutral (N) as much as 23.7%, disagree (TS) as much as 8.8 %, and strongly disagree (STS) as much as 1.0%. Based on the average percentage of respondents who answered strongly agree (SS) and agree (S) it proves that respondents have positive perceptions of the organization and positive perceptions of career paths through Pamobvit Polda XYZ. The statement with the largest value according to the respondent's perception is statement item number 1 at 33.9% while the statement item with the smallest value according to the respondent's perception is statement item number 2 at 22.5%.

Individual motivation variable data shows that the average respondents who answered strongly agree (SS) were 32.8%, agreed (S) was 47.9%, were neutral (N) was 16.2%, disagreed (TS) was 2.4%, and strongly disagree (STS) as much as 0.7%. Based on the answers of respondents

who answered strongly agree (SS) and agree (S) it proved that respondents had high motivation to carry out their duties as Pamobvit Polda XYZ personnel. The statement that received the greatest approval from the respondents regarding the motivation variable was statement item number 6 at 7335.7% while the statement item with the smallest value according to the respondent was statement item number 5 at 30.7%

Based on the individual performance variable data table, it can be seen that the average respondents who answered strongly agree (SS) were 39.9%, those who answered agreed (S) were 48.9%, were neutral (N) was 10.7%, and did notes. Agree (TS) as much as 0.47%, and strongly disagree (STS) as much as 0%. Based on the answers of respondents who answered strongly agree (SS) and those who answered agreed (S) reached, it shows that the performance of Ditpamobvit Polda XYZ personnel is good. The statement that shows the greatest agreement according to the respondent is statement item number 6 at 46.8%, while the statement item with the lowest value according to the respondent is statement item number 2 at 33.6%.

4.2. Validity and Reliability

This test covers construct validity testing (convergent validity and discriminant validity) and construct reliability testing using the outer model. The convergent validity test show that all of the research indicators have an outer loading > 0.7 . Except for one performance indicator, which has a value of 0.186. Whereas an indicator is acknowledged to meet convergent validity with a good category if it has an outer loading value > 0.7 .

Therefore, to maximize the AVE value, the variable indicator with the lowest outer loading value is committed. With a condition where all indicator variables have an outer loading value > 0.7 , then all indicators are acknowledged as feasible for use in research and can be used for further analysis. Furthermore, based on the processing of discriminant validity test data using the AVE of each research variable, a value of > 0.5 . Thus, it can be stated that each variable has good convergent validity.

Research reliability testing using composite reliability can be seen that the composite reliability value on all research variables is more than 0.7 which indicates that each variable is reliable and is included in the highly reliable category.

The reliability test was built-up by the Cronbach Alpha value which showed that the Cronbach alpha value of each research variable was 0.7. These results showed that each research variable has fulfilled the requirements of the Cronbach alpha value. Thus it can be summarized that all variables have a good level of reliability.

4.3. Inner Model Evaluation

Hypothesis testing is obtained out according to the results of the Inner Model (structural model) test that covers r-square output, parameter coefficients, and t-statistics. Whether a hypothesis can be accepted or rejected, among others, can be seen by focusing to the significance value between constructs, t-statistics, and p-values. These values can be seen from the following bootstrapping results:

Figure 2: Inner Model

The inner model schema (Figure 2) stated that the largest t-statistic value is indicated by the Motivation variable towards Performance, which is 10.125. The next biggest effect is the effect of perception on the motivation variable, which is 5,641. While the smallest effect is shown in the Perception variable on the performance of 1.121. According to calculations, to measure the R-Square value of endogenous variables, the following values are obtained:

Table 2: Value of R-Square

Variable	R-Square Value
Motivation	0.379
Performance	0.461

Source: SmartPLS data processing results, 2022

Chin (1998) stated that the results of R Square > 0.67 for endogenous latent variables in the structural model indicated the effect of exogenous variables on endogenous variables included in the good category. Meanwhile, 0.33 – 0.67, is included in the modest category; and the weak category if the R Square value is 0.19 – 0.33.

Thus, the Attitude variable and the Perception variable have a moderate effect on the Motivation variable. Meanwhile, the Attitude variable, the Perception variable, and the Motivation variable together have a moderate effect on the Performance variable.

4.4. Hypothesis testing

The direct influence of Attitudes and Perceptions on Motivation and performance, as well as Motivation on performance can be seen from the following table:

Table 3: Direct Effects

Hypothesis	Influence	Original Sample	T-Statistics	P-Values	Results
H1	Attitude <= Performance	0.097	1,585	0.114	Rejected
H2	Attitude => Motivation	0.345	4,912	0.000	Accepted
H3	Perception => Motivation	0.380	5,641	0.000	Accepted
H4	Motivation => Performance	0.585	10,125	0.000	Accepted
H5	Perception <= Performance	0.066	1,121	0.263	Rejected

Source: SmartPLS data processing results, 2022

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the Attitude variable has a negative effect on the performance of $1,585 < 1.96$. The attitude variable has a positive and significant effect on the motivation of $4.912 > 1.96$. The perception variable has a positive and significant effect on the motivation of $5,641 > 1.96$. The motivation variable has a positive and significant effect on the performance of $10.125 > 1.96$. The perception variable has a negative effect on employee performance of $1.121 < 1.96$. The indirect effect of Attitudes and Perceptions on Performance through Motivation can be seen from the total indirect effects which are presented in the following table:

Table 4: Indirect Influence

Hypothesis	Effect	Original Sample	T-Statistics	P-Values	Result
H6	Attitude => Performance	0.201	4,235	0.000	Accepted
H7	Perception => Performance	0.222	4,940	0.000	Accepted

Source: SmartPLS data processing results, 2022

Based on table 4, it can be seen that motivation can mediate the influence between attitude and employee performance of $4.235 > 1.96$. This shows that attitude can advance performance if individual personnel have high motivation. Motivation can also mediate the effect of perception with personnel performance of $4.940 > 1.96$. This shows that perception can advance performance if individual personnel have high motivation.

4.5. Results and Discussion

Attitude is the way a person expresses or applies their ideology and values through words and behaviors (Moise, 2017). Meanwhile, in the view of Kreitner & Kinicki (2003), attitude is defined as 'the impulse to respond consistently to something to support or not support it by focus to a particular object'. The results of the study found that individual attitudes about the organization had no effect on the individual performance of personnel in the Ditpamobvit Polda XYZ organization. Individual attitudes regarding the organization are not a determinant of personnel performance in carrying out their duties within the Ditpamobvit Polda XYZ organization.

Based on the results of the study, it was found that individual attitudes about the organization had a significant and positive effect on individual motivation in carrying out tasks at the Ditpamobvit Polda XYZ organization. Individual attitudes are evaluative statements - either agreeable or disagreeable - about objects, community, or circumstances (Robbins, 2003: 90). When organizations are perceived as providing benefits to individuals, individuals tend to be motivated to do their jobs well. Thus, the attitude becomes a positive contribution to the formation of one's motivation. The results of the study found that individual perceptions of the organization had a significant and positive effect on individual motivation in carrying out tasks in the Ditpamobvit Polda XYZ environment.

Perception as the process by which an employee organizes and interprets his impressions to give meaning to his environment and thus, it influences behavior in the workplace significantly (Langton & Robbins, 2006). Perception is nearly related to attitude. Perception is the process by which individuals interpret and organize sensations to produce valuable world experiences (Ilahi & Ahmad, 2016). Based on the results of the study, it was found that a person's motivation had a significant and positive effect on his performance. In this case the motivation of a Pamobvit personnel will have a significant and positive effect on their performance within the Ditpamobvit Polda XYZ organizational environment. The right motivation for individual employees will be the driving force to achieve high performance. A positive and significant relationship between motivation and performance is shown in the research of Saluy, Musanti, & Mulyana, , 2019).

Employee performance is the ability of employees to demonstrate certain skills. Employee performance is very decisive because with this performance it will be known the extent of his capability to carry out the tasks assigned to him (Sinambela, 2016: 480). However, based on the results of the study, it was found that individual perceptions had no significant and positive effect on individual performance in the Ditpamobvit Polda XYZ organization..

Although individual attitudes have no direct effect on performance, the results of this study found an indirect influence on individual attitude variables on performance mediated by motivation variables. Thus, motivation plays a full mediating role so that attitudes can contribute to performance. Similarly, individual perception, although it has no positive and significant effect on performance, but based on the results of the study obtained the value of the indirect effect of the Perception variable on performance. This shows that the motivation variable can mediate the influence between employee perceptions and performance. Motivation plays a full mediating role so that perception can contribute to improving performance.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Based on several findings from research results and explanations in previous chapters, it can be summarize that there is a positive and significant relationship between individual attitudes towards individual motivation in the Ditpamobvit Polda XYZ organizational environment. A positive and significant relationship also occurs between the individual's perception of individual motivation variables and between individual motivation variables on individual

performance in the Ditpamobvit Polda XYZ environment. While the positive effect, although indirect, can be seen between the Attitude and Perception variables on the personnel performance variable in the Ditpamobvit Polda XYZ organization.

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